

ESSENCE, TYPES OF COMMUNICATION AND FEATURES OF FORMING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS

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Annotation: The first and the foremost thing which ought to be highlighted that a communication is the act of transferring information from one place or person to another. The purpose of the scientific work is to reveal the essence of communication, and to analyze its types and aspects of use, as well as the characteristics of the formation of communicative skills.

Index Terms- communication, formation, communicative skill, verbal and oral communication, speech, linguadidactics, form.

Humanity communicates with a purpose of getting or conveying a message. When human beings talk to each other, the first thing which comes to one's mind is absolutely fluency. That could be because it is a vitally important aspect of what good communicative skill includes. Whether communication is verbal or oral, people still encounter some barriers to comprehend the message while communicating with each other since communication could be expressed in various ways such as communicating ambiguously i.e. not to the exact point or with a number of meanings. Some prefer modulating their voice while talking to in order to convey a message in a more precise way and to match their sentences.

Another main characteristic about a communication which make those people who are using some languages as a foreign or a second language to talk to somebody is that making some errors while communicating but they still do not pay attention to grammatical mistakes since it is necessary how to use a language to transfer information to any listeners and keep communicating without hesitation.

As it is mentioned above, communication can be passed on information to other people in a broad range of ways as it is considered to be a main aspect of human being. It could be several types which each of them plays an essential role to transfer information. Here are included the most widely-used types:

verbal;

oral;

Each of them is used in diverse purposes such as a daily usage in social life i.e. at home, school, and work and so on. The most widely-used ones are verbal and oral since orally-communicating using his or her voice is the easiest way to pass on a message quicker. Whereas in contrast, a verbal communication could be the easiest way to convey information with the help of some networks, paper or such related things. Another kind of communication named visual consists of graphs, charts, logos and so on. Above mentioned types of communication are used effectively by humanity on a daily basis and used with different purposes to transfer information to other people.

Skill is a way of doing an action. In linguodidactic testing, the object of control is communicative skills, which might be understood as the ability of a person to carry out a speech action to solve certain communicative tasks derived from acquired skills and knowledge. The skill is formed through exercises and creates the ability to perform actions.

Having studied the different interpretation of the concept of “Skill”, it may be decided to use the following definition of this concept: “Skill is the mastery of the methods (techniques, actions) of applying acquired knowledge in practice”. Various communicative aspects were already considered at the beginning of the development of methodological ideas by O. A. Alexandrova, M. V. Grigoryeva, and M. E.

Dashkin. They believed that one of the most important goals of education should be precisely the preparation of pupils for practical activities¹.

In the works of M. V. Grigoryeva, communicative skills are understood as the ability to correctly, intelligibly, adequately and competently convey one's thought, to perceive information from communication participants in interpersonal communication.²

According to G. M. Andreyeva, communicative skills are a complex of conscious communicative actions, which are based on a sufficiently high theoretical and practical readiness of the person, contributing to the creative use of knowledge to reflect and transform reality.³

A. V. Mudrik defines the concept of communicative skills as skills associated with the correct alignment of their behavior i.e. it is necessary to understand human psychology: to be able to choose the right intonation and gestures correctly, to be able to understand other people, to try to predict the reaction of the interlocutor, to imagine oneself in his/her place, to be able to correctly choose the most correct way to address different interlocutors. [31, pp.33]

The primary sources of communicative skills from rhetorical positions are rhetorical skills, namely:

1. The ability to invent and find material;
2. The ability to arrange material in the correct (logical) sequence;
3. The ability to consistently express thoughts;
4. The ability to memorize pre-prepared speech;

¹ Mikerova G. Zh., Brusentsova O. L. Diagnostics of communicative universal educational actions of schoolchildren // Modern problems of science and education. - 2015. - No. 6. - Pp. 542-542.

² Grigoryeva M. V. Development of communicative skills // Secondary School. - 2003. - No. 10. - P. 103.

³ Andreeva G. M. Social psychology. - M.: Aspect Press, 2001. P. 64.

5. The ability to deliver a prepared speech using sound means of emotional-semantic expressiveness (A. R. Luria, A. V. Mudrik, A. A. Leontyev).⁴

According to A. V. Mudrik, the components of communicative skills include: objective perception of people (understanding of their character and mood); orientation of partners; the ability to correctly understand the communicational situation (to understand the rules, to establish new contacts); to cooperate in various types of activities (plan and set goals) and to analyze what has been achieved.⁵

N. I. Zhinkin believed that there was a need to pay attention to what pupils say and how they respond to the actions and actions of other people. It is necessary to identify their thoughts and feelings that accompany the schoolchildren's acts of their communication with other people, their difficulties that they encounter when coming into contact with others. He defined the external and internal components of communication. External components include verbal (speech utterances) and non-verbal forms of behavior (tone of voice, pace of speech, facial expressions and gestures).⁶

Communication between different people is a complex socio-psychological process, which is carried out through two parts: speech (verbal) and non-speech (non-verbal), they mutually complement and enrich each other.

Verbal communication skills are the ability to interact, built on lexically allocated units (words): oral (speech) and written (text). Speaking is the most common way of communication. In order for a person to understand, it is not enough to have a good diction. A person must be clearly aware of what exactly he/she wants to say, and he/she must also be able to choose such words so that his/her thought is correctly perceived by the interlocutor. If the pupil is to speak in front of the class,

⁴ Vasilieva V. S. Theoretical and pedagogical aspects of the formation of communicative competence of teachers of school educational organizations // *Science, Education, Society*. - 2015. - No. 4. - Pp. 80-94.

⁵ Mudrik A.V. *Communication as a factor in the education of students*. - M., Enlightenment, 1984. P. 33.

⁶ Derekleeva N.I. *The development of the communicative culture of students in the lesson and in extracurricular activities*. - M. 2005. P. 16.

he or she prepares abstracts for him/herself, but in everyday life, oral communication occurs spontaneously, and often among most children this can cause anxiety, self-doubt and fear. It is necessary to expand the vocabulary in order for an oral speech not to provoke difficulties. With a clear understanding of what he/she wants to say, and with a sufficiently large vocabulary, he/she will probably be able to correctly express his/her thought and to avoid possible misunderstandings.

Fairly an important ability associated with an oral speech is the ability to retain the attention of listeners. While providing a message, it is necessary to look into one of the listeners' eyes directly, only then reciprocal attention will be guaranteed, and, conversely, when pronouncing his/her thoughts in a monotone voice, resting on a text prepared in advance, it will be found that the listeners are not paying attention. It is important to maintain a visual contact with the interlocutors since this allows the speaker to evaluate the response of the listeners.

Written messages have a great advantage over oral messages. When writing a written message, it is possible to think through it, put your thoughts in order, and, if necessary, rewrite it. Writing has its drawbacks. It cannot convey voice intonation and gestures, and there is no possibility of instant feedback from the reader.

Verbal communication is available only to humans and as a prerequisite requires knowledge of the language. The result of verbal communication is traced in how much the communicator mastered the ability to correctly put his/her speech, as well as his/her personal characteristics. At the moment, a good command of the speech remains the most important professional component of a person.⁷

Non-verbal communication is a system of symbols, signs that are used to convey a message and designed to more fully understand it, they are to some extent independent of the psychological and socio-psychological qualities of a person.

⁷ Sternin I.A. Types of communicative actions and communicative behavior of a person, // Pragmatic aspects of the functioning of language units. M., 1991. Pp. 41-43.

Non-verbal communication is one of the means by which a person represents his/her "I". With the help of it, interpersonal influence takes place, relations are regulated, an image of a communication partner is created. Non-verbal communication acts as a clarification, it is ahead of verbal communication and is an additional source of information in relation to verbal communication. Non-verbal communication does not provide for the use of sound speech, natural language as a means of communication. Non-verbal communication is a communication through facial expressions, gestures and pantomimes (poses), which are carried out through direct bodily or sensory contacts (tactile, visual, auditory, olfactory, and other sensations and images that we receive from another person). In this case, non-verbal communication is carried out only by personal contact. Means of non-verbal communication can accompany speech, and can be used separately from verbal means.⁸

The formation of communicative skills of pupils remains an urgent problem since the level of formation of communicative skills affects not only the effectiveness of children's education, but also the process of their socialization and personality development in general. Skills are formed in the course of activity, and communicative skills are formed and improved in the direct process of communication.

Formation is the process of shaping something; in a broad sense, formation is understood as any process in which stability is given to something, completeness, a certain type or something which is created, organized, composed or combined.

The speech should be built in accordance with current expectations, which is essential for the formation of communicative skills. It is advisable to educate children through the ability to listen to and hear interlocutors, to be patient with their opinions, and it is also necessary to encourage children to express their point of view.

⁸ Sternin I.A. Types of communicative actions and communicative behavior of a person, // Pragmatic aspects of the functioning of language units. M., 1991. Pp. 41-43.

The main role in this is played by the teacher since he/she provides students with speech patterns, helps them in conducting discussions, various disputes and bringing arguments. The formation of the communicative skills is influenced by various forms and methods.

The formation of communicative skills in the process of communicative activities such as role-playing, disputing, etc. among pupils is carried out by the stages and consists of the followings:

- disclosure to pupils of the meaning of communicative skills;
- familiarization of pupils with the content and structure of skills in the distribution of roles;
- the inclusion in the implementation of joint gaming tasks to master communicative skills;
- improvement of the communicative skills acquired by schoolchildren in their creative activities.⁹

The formation of communicative skills is greatly influenced by training sessions. Training is a method of active learning, which is aimed at the development of knowledge, skills and social attitudes. Trainings are of various types and they are created for specific goals and tasks.

Communicative training is a training that is aimed at developing the ability to communicate with other people. Communicative training contributes to the development of the ability to exchange information with other people, creating the conditions for the most efficient transmission of information. Communicative training includes the theory and practice of managing social communications, that is, communication with other people. During the communicative training, effective processes for communication are developed and built up, the image of a person and

⁹ Kidron A.A. Communicative ability and its improvement. - Dis. Cond. The psycho. Science. Leningrad. 1981. Pp. 20-21.

his/her attitude to other people are formed and maintained and skills to reach agreement, cooperation and recognition are developed.¹⁰

Communication is an indispensable component of human life. Communicative training is aimed at harmonizing relationships and relationships of a person with other people, establishing and optimizing relationships with people in accordance with their goals. One of the tasks of a trainer in the formation of communication skills is to establish friendships; it should help them develop an interest in everything that happens, create an atmosphere of goodwill, trust and mutual respect, initiative, as well as the ability to communicate correctly.

After doing a number of tasks in terms of communicative training young generation will learn:

1. How to correctly use communicative means to solve various problems;
2. To understand that other people have their own point of view, which may not coincide with his/her own;
3. To take into account different opinions of other people and strive for cooperation;
4. To formulate their own opinion and position;
5. To agree and come to a common decision in joint activities, including in a situation of interest;
6. To ask questions;
7. To use speech to regulate their actions; adequately use speech means to solve various communicative problems, to build a monologic statement and their own dialogical form of speech.¹¹

¹⁰ Fomicheva M.F. Training the correct pronunciation of children. M., Enlightenment, 1991. Pp. 108-109.

¹¹ Voyushina M.L. The formation of the ability to analyze the artworks of schoolchildren - AKD, SP b., 1989. Pp. 12-15.

Thus, by communicative skills it is understood: the ability to listen to an interlocutor, to justify and express one's own opinion, to formulate one's thoughts in oral and written speech, to highlight essential guidelines for action in a speech, and to convey them to a partner and group interaction skills. Communicative skills are formed in the process of communication. The concept of "communication" in the psychological and pedagogical literature do not have any differences. Scientists have identified verbal and non-verbal communication skills, which are formed in the oral and symbolic form of communication. Communicative skills as the ability to listen and express their thoughts, the ability to behave correctly in various conflict situations, and to work in a group are characteristic. If these communicative skills of the learner are formed at a low level of development, then it is advisable to use special forms and methods of their formation corresponding to that age. The use of forms (training, group, individual and collective work), and methods (conversation, role and didactic games, project activities), which ensure the inclusion in communicative activities, is obtained through the gradual formation of communicative skills, based on the expansion of their communicative motives, knowledge, needs and gradually increasing communicative activity.

To sum up, as it is mentioned above, there is a broad range of meanings of communication and communicative skill which are defined by various sources and scholars as well as including some features and different types of communication which can be used to elicit or convey the message.

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